

ENHANCING OSMTRACKER BY SHARING TRACES TO A GITHUB REPOSITORY

JEAN MARCO ROJAS UMAÑA¹
JAIME GUTIÉRREZ ALFARO²

¹LabComún, Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica – jeanmarco1997@gmail.com

²LabComún, Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica – jgutierrez@itcr.ac.cr

OSMTracker is a GPS data capture application for Android that generates GPX files containing waypoints and points of interest recorded during a route, as well as geolocated multimedia files such as voice recordings and pictures. The application is designed to simplify the data capture process for novice users, while allowing experienced mappers to customize the tool's functionality. OSMTracker is available in popular Android software repositories such as F-Droid and the Google Play Store. According to the Play Store statistics, the app has 12.9 thousand active users worldwide. OSMTracker plays a significant role in open-source mapping by enabling users to collect and contribute data to OpenStreetMap (OSM). The customization capabilities of OSMTracker enable it to adapt to diverse thematic mapping requirements, making it a versatile tool for community-driven mapping initiatives. Many thematic mapping tools require a certain level of expertise in GIS, software programming, or advanced digital literacy for manipulating files on mobile devices, which can be a barrier for novice users. Customizing apps for the needs of both novice and experienced users is a way of lowering barriers without losing flexibility to support advanced uses. For instance, in [1] the authors implement a plugin in Leaflet providing a user-friendly solution for creating thematic maps. They combine data classification, symbology, and legend creation into a single, streamlined process, offering a high level of customization and ease of use for both novice and experienced users. OSM Sidewalkreator plugin [2] was designed with customizability in mind, allowing users to have significant control over the mapping process and adapt the tool to meet their specific needs. OSMTracker is very useful for thematic mapping in combination with participatory cartography methodologies. The app became part of the methodological resources used by the Laboratorio Experimental de Computación y Comunidades (LabComún) for the development of public university extension projects together with communities. Naturally, using the app in this context, showed us improvements required in the app to simplify the mapping process for fostering community participation. In example, during the mapping join project with Erizo Juan Santamaría informal settlement community [3], an improvement in how custom buttons layouts are downloaded and installed was coded to encourage broader participation [4]. In a common workflow during a mapping process with OSMTracker, experienced users create customized buttons layouts for the specific thematic and upload them to GitHub. Collaborators with less experience can easily download and install them directly from the repository within the app menu. After the mapping fieldwork is completed, expert mappers collect all the data recorded by individuals and process it according to the mapping goal. Within the app, there is no easy way to gather all the data. One alternative is that every mapper uploads the GPX files (without multimedia) to OpenStreetMap, and then, the person in charge of the mapping process downloads the files for consolidating them together. However, to accomplish this, OSM usernames of all the participant mappers must be known beforehand. Another alternative is that every mapper will export their collected files (GPX traces and georeferenced multimedia) into a folder on their phone and then copy the files to a shared folder, manually. This complexity, aroused during the LabComún join project with Alajuela en Cleta urban cycling collective, and motivated the need to improve OSMTracker by adding a functionality to upload geospatial recorded files to a server, different from OSM. We present an enhancement that has been implemented in OSMTracker to upload GPX and multimedia files to a specific GitHub repository. The research includes a broader validation of the need for the functionality, software design, and implementation in the app. To explore in depth the need for sharing traces into a folder in the cloud, a survey targeting OSM community members was conducted. The survey was distributed through OSM Telegram chats, mailing lists, and OSMTracker social media. A total of 60 answers were received. The results validated the necessity, 78% of the responders agreed on the usefulness of the improvement

described. Furthermore, the survey indicates that it is a common practice (56.9% of the responders) to process captured traces before uploading them to OSM. This is accomplished by exporting the trace from OSMTracker to a phone local folder, and subsequent to processing or editing the trace, uploading it to OSM using another software tool. Regarding the downloading of OSM GPX traces from various mapping collaborators, 29.4% of the respondents utilized that workflow after a mapping process. Ultimately, after confirming the necessity for the functionality, GitHub was deemed the more suitable service to centralize the traces gathered by the team during a mapping process. The feature was implemented in OSMTracker, enabling users to upload traces and multimedia files, compressed together into a zip file, to a GitHub repository. In the easiest way to use the functionality, a user can select the target repository in OSMTracker, add a comment, and commit the geospatial files. The only requirement is that collaborators are added to a GitHub repository, which is accomplished in the GitHub settings by the owner of the repository. Advanced options allow users, directly from OSMTracker, to create a new repository or fork an existing one, and make pull requests with the zip file. The graphic interface elements maintained the consistent look and feel of the application. Prior to implementation, the proposal was conceptualized in Figma and disseminated to the OSMTracker GitHub community for feedback. The functionality was implemented in a separate code branch with an open pull request to the OSMTracker official GitHub code repository. The code is freely available under the GNU GPLv3 license. OSMTracker's upload to GitHub functionality keeps barriers low for new mappers when sharing their field work traces, while at the same time opening new options for advanced users with specific needs. GitHub provides various levels of privacy, security, and data management, and despite not being intended for the storage of geospatial data, it is a widely utilized service for sharing algorithms and their required data. By centralizing traces in a GitHub repository, software code integrations can easily process collected geospatial data before publishing it into an OSM or other specific map. This enhancement holds particular significance for crowdsourcing mapping, as it enables novel workflows for processing traces while maintaining the simplicity of the OSMTracker GPS capture tool.

Keywords: OpenStreetMap; Thematic mapping; GPX Traces; Community-driven mapping; OpenSource Mapping.

References

- [1] BALLA, Dániel; GEDE, Mátyás. *Beautiful thematic maps in Leaflet with automatic data classification*. The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, v. XLVIII-4/W12-2024, p. 3–10, 20 jun. 2024. DOI <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLVIII-4-W12-2024-3-2024>
- [2] DE MORAES VESTENA, Kauê; CAMBOIM, Silvana Philippi; RODRIGUES DOS SANTOS, Daniel. *OSM Sidewalkreator: A QGIS plugin for an automated drawing of sidewalk networks for OpenStreetMap*. European Journal of Geography, v. 14, n. 4, p. 66–84, 12 dez. 2023. DOI <https://doi.org/10.48088/ejg.k.ves.14.4.066.084>
- [3] GUTIÉRREZ ALFARO, Jaime. *Study Case of Erizo Juan Santamaría: from free map to official cartography*. Free and Open Source Software for Geospatial 2024 (FOSS4G 2024), 2 dez. 2024. DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14226033>
- [4] OVIEDO SANCHEZ, Brandon et al. *Promoting community participation in thematic mapping processes by simplifying the free software tool OSMTracker for Android*. IV Jornadas Costarricenses de Investigación en Computación e Informática (JoCICI), ago. 2019. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1109/JoCICI48395.2019.9105207>